

A Short Grammar of ʕUiʕuid

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This grammar constitutes a brief introduction into the constructed language ʕUiʕuid, literally the ‘true language’. The present grammar is based on the second conceptual phase out of three in my language development. In the third stage, there are only minor changes in the phonology but some important ones in the system of verbal derivation, an expansion of grammatical cases, and a reduction of infixes in the nominal derivational system. Yet, the second ʕUiʕuid stage still poses the most advanced language system. This is why this phase has been chosen for a concise grammatical description.

It should be noted that the variety of ʕUiʕuid presented here is actually Standard ʕUiʕuid, i.e. the lingua franca in the homeland of the ʕUiʕuid speakers after the expulsion of the so-called Nikate (a ʕUiʕuid exonym for several tribes which have invaded large parts of the ʕUiʕuid language area). Standard ʕUiʕuid shares many parallels with certain dialects in the time before the Nikate invasion but is not identical to it. Standard ʕUiʕuid and other contemporary ʕUiʕuid varieties were situated in diglossia.

Why read this conlang grammar? Even if ʕUiʕuid is neither a living language nor at least a language which was once alive but a constructed language, I think this grammar is worth reading. The reader might find some joy and fascination in this piece of art, so I hope. Although inspired by several natural languages, this naturalistic a priori conlang is not a portrait of a natlang but stands for itself. I included only features I like, or I find interesting. For instance, the phoneme inventory is very symmetric which is on one side quite natural, on the other side very pleasing for my own sense of aesthetics. To give further examples, my decisions for the presence of pharyngeals, some degree of templatic morphology, and for a relative tense system are all due to my own linguistic taste.

Here, I want to give a short description of ʕUiʕuid. I suppose its hallmarks are the following:

- The presence of the pharyngeal fricatives /ħ/ and /ʕ/
- Virtually all verbal roots have the shape CVCV
- Metathesis of the first or second syllable carries morphosyntactic meaning
- The presence of infixes
- Morphological mora insertion
- “Enucleation” of non-low vowels preceding a stressed vowel

1. Phonology

1.1 Consonant Inventory

In the following, the consonantal phonemes of ʒUɪʒuid are shown. If IPA and the transcription used here diverge, the phonetic symbol is indicated in brackets.

	Labial	Coronal		Velar	Pharyngeal
Voiceless stops	p	t		g (g)	
Voiced stops	b	d		k	
Voiceless fricatives	f	s		x	ħ
Voiced fricatives	v	z		ɣ	ʕ
Nasals	m	n	ɲ (ɲ)		
Trills		r			
Approximants	w	l	y (j)		

You can see that there is an unusually high number of fricatives (i.e. 8). With 21 consonants, this approximately corresponds to the mean value of the world's languages. Without phonemic status are [ʔ] and [h]. In my transcription, double letters indicate lengthened articulation for both consonants and vowels.

In my original draft, voiceless stops were aspirated. In the second conceptual phase, I still stucked to this but had a slightly weaker aspiration in mind. This has led to my abandonment of aspiration as default feature in the third conceptual phase. Now, stops only get aspiration in syllable final position if released at all.

In the coda position, the velar stops receive the feature [-high] and, hence, become their uvular counterparts [χ ʁ].

In the second stage of ʒUɪʒuid, the alveolar stops /t d/ become dental fricatives in intervocalic position, i.e. [θ ð]. This has been removed in the third conceptual phase.

A note about pharyngeal dissimilation. If a word contains more than one pharyngeal, two dissimilation processes can take place. In case of identical pharyngeals, the second one is realised as [h]. A prominent example is the language name ʒUɪʒuid, phonetically being [ʒui.ɦuid]. If both /ʕ/ and /ħ/ are present, the voiceless pharyngeal fricative remains stable whereas /ʕ/ is dissimilated to [h].

1.2 Vowel Inventory

There are five phonemic vowels: /a e i o u/—thus, a pretty average vowel system. In closed syllables, the non-low vowels are slightly lax. If /e/ and /o/ are lengthened, they are minimally raised. In monomoraic positions, they are actually [e] and [o]. All vowels can be short or long.

	Front	Back
High	i	u
Middle	e	o
Low	a	

1.3 Syllable Structure

The maximal syllable in ᚼᚱᚹᚾᚹᚾ is CVVC. Onsets are obligatory if the syllable is in a stressed position or word-initial. Elsewhere, there are also empty onsets though some speakers insert glides as onset if the syllable follows a non-low vowel, e.g. in *daguuat* ‘we (excl.) build’ being [da.ˈgu:wat]. In such cases after low vowels, epenthetic *h* occurs, as in *ta<h>uuᚼ* ‘fingers’.

As one can see, ᚼᚱᚹᚾᚹᚾ has not too complex syllables. The most common one is CV. But CVV and CVC are permitted, as well. Branching onsets and codas, however, are entirely absent. So, neither CCV or VCC. The only possible nucleus poses any vowel including diphthongs. Standard ᚼᚱᚹᚾᚹᚾ exhibits multiple diphthongs, both raising and falling. In many dialects of the classical period, the diphthongs /ao/ and /ae/ were phonetically distinct from /au/ and /ai/ but merged in most of the dialects in modern times. Thus, Standard ᚼᚱᚹᚾᚹᚾ most often does not distinguish between /au/ ~ /ao/ and /ai/ ~ /ae/ being typically pronounced [ai] ~ [au] or [aɪ] ~ [aø].

1.4 Stress

§1. Stress (or better *accent*) is basically on the stem. Inflectional endings do not usually attract stress. This is important because ᚼᚱᚹᚾᚹᚾ largely obeys the stress-to-weight principle but seems to violate it in unstressed heavy inflectional endings. Having a stratal architecture of ᚼᚱᚹᚾᚹᚾ stress assignment in mind, a moraic trochee from right to left holds true.

§2. To give an impression of stress assignment, let us look at *guniseñar* ‘he/she/it makes/lets sb. wash (oneself)’, which is pronounced as [(,gu.ni).(‘se.nar)]. However, it cannot be neglected that many ʕUiʕuid speakers impose their respective dialectal stress pattern on the standard and do not place the moraic foot directly from right to left but include extrametricality of the last syllable. In other words: The final syllable should not be part of a metrical foot in these dialects, resulting in forms like [gu.(‘ni.se).nar].

§3. Note that nominal plural suffixes belong to the stem domain—both segmental and reduplicative plurals, as visible in *hiisoo* ‘questions’ or *dauguug* ‘buildings’ with accent on the final syllable.

§4. The split between the stem level and the word level seems to run between roots, derivational morphology, and inherent inflection on the one hand and contextual inflection on the other hand. This is why, for example, *daguar* ‘he/she/it builds’ is pronounced as [‘da.g^war] and not as *[da.‘g^war] or *[da.‘g^war] since it consists of *dagu-* ‘to build’ and *-ar* being the exponent of the 3rd person.

Another example poses the prefix conjugation for the so-called past tense. If we impose a moraic trochee over the stem (such as *-aḥwa*) and then add the personal prefix *si-*, we get the correct form *siaḥwa* ‘he/she/it needed’. So, /aḥwa/ → [(‘aḥ).wa] which is the base for the following derivation: /si+(‘aḥ).wa/ → [(‘siaḥ).wa], not *[(‘siaḥ).wa].

§5. A notable feature related to stress is what I call enucleation. If a non-low vowel is in an unstressed position it will be reduced to a palatal or labial feature, respectively, as long as the phonotactic restrictions are not violated. Assuming extrametricality of word final consonants, this can be exemplified as follows:

Another example may pose *duiḥ* ‘victory’ vs. *duiḥh* ‘victories’, in IPA: [duiḥ] vs. [d^wi:ḥ]. This pattern is highly characteristic of nominal plurality in ʕUiʕuid.

2. Morphology

As has been mentioned, ʕUiʕuid is a root-inflecting language. Most roots in the second phase follow the CVCV pattern, which is the base for the “present” tense and the citation form I use. Below, a list of some verbs is to be found:

<i>dagu-</i>	‘to build’
<i>duma-</i>	‘to sit’
<i>eba-</i>	‘to come’
<i>fagi-</i>	‘to extinguish, destroy’
<i>gora-</i>	‘to seek, search for’
<i>ħawa-</i>	‘to need’
<i>ħisi-</i>	‘to ask’
<i>ħuma-</i>	‘to steal’
<i>yapi-</i>	‘to put, lay down’
<i>yeya-</i>	‘to have, hold, possess’
<i>laxo-</i>	‘to die’
<i>mixa-</i>	‘to think, find’
<i>muna-</i>	‘to open (trans.)’
<i>rumi-</i>	‘to see’
<i>sito-</i>	‘to eat’
<i>tuni</i>	‘to go back, return’
<i>xoyu-</i>	‘to know’
<i>selo-</i>	‘to save’
<i>toħa-</i>	‘to waver, sway’
<i>vuʕa-</i>	‘to be splendid, superb’

A note on root structure. In the beginning of the creation of ʕUiʕuid, I planned a quite strict association between the CVCV structure with verbs and the CVVC with nouns. This has partly been relaxed in the second conceptual phase and even more in the third one. In the last conceptual stage, one can see that many simple nouns have the shape CVC or CVCV. Some of the CVC forms go back to old *CVCə forms.

2.1 Nominal Derivation

ƳUiƳuid has several ways of deriving words—both in nominal and verbal morphology. As we shall see, there are typical pairs of form and meaning associated with a characteristic word formation. However, a clear prediction of the specific meaning is impossible since derivational morphology is generally not as regular and productive as inflection. If we see a pattern typical of—let us say—instrumental nouns, the instrumental semantics can be obscured by language change so that we would put it in other semantic categories. Moreover, there might be several ways of expressing the same derivational function, often accompanied by more or less productive affixes. Nonetheless, ƳUiƳuid’s derivational system offers rational guidelines for connecting words.

2.1.1 Nomen Simplex

§1. ƳUiƳuid’s derivation heavily builds on (abstract) roots. This makes it even more important to understand its root structure. The root *ist* is most visible in verb stems. All native “basic” verbs have the shape CVCV, such as *dagu-* ‘to build’, *tena-* ‘to kill’, or *Ƴudi-* ‘to speak’ (see above). Simple nouns can be derived by metathesis of the second root syllable. The corresponding nouns of these verbs are *daug* ‘building, big house’, *tean* ‘murder’, and *Ƴuid* ‘language, speech, words’. Here are further examples:

Simple nouns

Verb	<i>duhi-</i> ‘to win, defeat’	<i>riso-</i> ‘to take, seize’	<i>boko-</i> ‘to bind’	<i>leru-</i> ‘to go’	<i>veli-</i> ‘to carry’
Noun	<i>duih</i> ‘victory’	<i>rios</i> ‘hand’	<i>book</i> ‘bond(s)’	<i>leur</i> ‘way, route’	<i>veil</i> ‘weight, burden’
Verb	<i>wiye-</i> ‘to travel by ship’	<i>Ƴoñi-</i> ‘to push, press’	<i>sibe-</i> ‘to hear’	<i>kata-</i> ‘to drink’	<i>wabe-</i> ‘to write’
Noun	<i>wiey</i> ‘ship’	<i>Ƴoiñ</i> ‘writing’	<i>sieb</i> ‘ear’	<i>kaat</i> ‘water’	<i>waeb</i> ‘book’

§2. As we see, the precise meaning is not fully predictable but is at least more or less comprehensible. We would expect, for example, the corresponding noun to *kata* ‘to drink’ having the meaning ‘drink, something to drink’. Furthermore, it is not clear whether the derived noun signifies a result, an instrument, or the act of doing something. It should be

noted that we cannot conclude the register or frequency of a word. The word *dagu-* ‘to build’ is pretty basic whereas *daug* ‘building’ is more specialised. The standard noun with the respective meaning and the largest distribution would be *yas* ‘house’. In other intricate cases, we can understand the relation of two words by looking at the culture of the ǁUǁui speakers. Since writing in (Coastal) ǁUǁui usually happens by pressing a stylus into clay, the connection between *ǁoiñi* ‘to push, press’ and *ǁoiñ* ‘writing’ makes sense.

2.1.2 Nomen Agentis

In the second developmental stage of ǁUǁui, agent nouns are formed by a circumfix *-n-...-t*. It loosely corresponds to English *-er*. Examples are *dunḥit* ‘winner’ (cf. *duḥi-* ‘to win’), *xonyut* ‘wise person, scholar’ (cf. *xoyu-* ‘to be wise’), *wanbet* ‘writer, secretary’ (cf. *wabe-* ‘to write’), *nenḥit* ‘retinue’ (cf. *neḥi-* ‘to accompany, help, support’). Nouns of this type belong to the reduplicative plural formation (R-plural), e.g. *dunḥitiit* ‘winners’ and *xonyutuut* ‘scholars’.

2.1.3 Nomen Loci

Whereas agent nouns feature a CV-*infix*-CV-*suffix* pattern, place nouns have the structure CV-*infix*-VC, to be more precise: CV-*r*-VC, as in *lerur* ‘path, road’ (cf. *leru-* ‘to go’), *sarik* ‘farm, grange’ (cf. *saki-* ‘to bound, enclose, fence’), *hiris* ‘oracle (place, not the person or the forseen words)’ (cf. *hisi-* ‘to ask’), *duram* ‘chair’ (cf. *duma-* ‘to sit’), probably *poris* ‘island’ of unknown origin. All nouns of this type are pluralised by lengthening the final vowel (L-plural), such as *poriis* ‘islands’, *leruur* ‘paths’, and *duraam* ‘chairs’.

2.1.4 Nomen Instrumentale

Very similarly to the formation of agent nouns, instrumental nouns consist of an infix and a suffix, too. The pattern is CV-*s*-CV-*l*. Here is an example with the verb *wabe-* ‘to write’: *wasbel* ‘stylus, pen, quill’. Note that metatheses often occur here, which essentially follow the syllable contact law. According to this, the *s*-infix and the consonant of the second root syllable exchange their position if the latter is a liquid, nasal or semivowel. Thus, *muna-* ‘open’ is not mapped on **musnal* but on *munsal* ‘key’. This kind of morphophonological metathesis may distantly remind of similar cases as the Hebrew *hitpa’el* and the Sidaama

suffix for the 1st person plural (cf. Hebrew *hištamer* ‘he guarded’ vs. **hiššamer* and Sidaama /got’+inémemo/ which is mapped on *gont’émemo* ‘we sleep’). In the following, you will find a short list of examples from ʕUiʕuid:

bisʕel ‘contract, certificate’, cf. *biʕe-* ‘to trade, merchandise’

dulsol ‘chariot, cart’, *dulo-* ‘to drive (a cart), ride’

ɣawsil ‘musical instrument; flute’, cf. *ɣawi-* ‘to sing, play (an instrument)’

issal ‘knife’, cf. *isa-* ‘to cut’

kastal ‘cup, drinking horn’, cf. *kata-* ‘to drink’

sistol ‘spoon’, cf. *sito-* ‘to eat’

tensal ‘weapon, sword’, cf. *tena-* ‘to kill’

velsil ‘bag, backpack’, cf. *veli-* ‘to carry’

simsal ‘plough’, cf. *gusima-* ‘to flourish, carry seeds’ (only attested in the causative stem)

The plural typically follows the lengthening pattern (L-plural) though some nouns, such as *simsal* → *simsalaal* ‘ploughs’, show an R-plural.

2.1.5 Nomen Emphaticum

The name ʕUiʕuid literally means ‘true language’ as has been mentioned. This kind of nominal derivation I call nomen emphaticum because it means the significatum is ‘true, proper, classic’. Other examples are *neineiħ* ‘true friend’, *barbar* ‘nemesis, arch-foe’, or *paulaul* ‘true king, Great King’. The respective nouns here are *ʕuid* ‘language, tongue’, *neiħ* ‘friend’, *bar* ‘enemy, foe’, and *paul* ‘king’.

For monosyllabic nouns, the noun is simply reduplicated whereby word-internal superheavy syllables are avoided by omitting the stem-final consonant. This is why **ʕuidʕuid*, **neiħneiħ*, and **paulpaul* are ungrammatical.

The plural is marked by applying the suffix *-oo* (O-plural). Stress is always on the first syllable in the singular. In the plural, the first syllable bears secondary stress, the last syllable main stress, such as *neineiħoo* ‘true friends’ as [(,nei).(,nei).('ħoo)] or *barbaroo* ‘arch-foes’ as [(,bar).ba.('roo)].

2.2 Verbal Derivation

Being no less regular than nominal derivation, deriving verbs follows more or less rigid lines, but an explicit prediction of verbal semantics based on the respective stem is not feasible. One word in general about paradigmatic gaps in the derived stems. Some of them seem to lack the respective Basic stem (B-stem) such as *niyatu-* ‘to be busy, occupied, engaged (not by marriage)’ (from Old ṢUiṢuid **yatu-* ‘to engage sb., keep sb. busy’), *gusezu-* ‘to tan’ (from Old ṢUiṢuid **sezu-* ‘to be sour, acid-like’), or *ruruvo-* ‘to sink’ (in Old ṢUiṢuid, it is just *ruvo-*).

All these cases show that once there was corresponding B-stem which fell into oblivion. Especially for the R-stem, reinforcement plays a role. In the beginning of these developments, speakers felt inclined to put more emphasis on some verbs by using the R-stem. However, these forms became so frequent that they pose the most common form in Standard ṢUiṢuid, and the old B-stem forms became obsolete.

2.2.1 The Valency Changing Stems

§1. Simple verbs have the shape CVCV as already explained above. In addition to the CVCV-stem—the B(asic)-stem—there are four verb stems that change the argument frame of the verb: causative (C-stem), mediopassive (M-stem), causative-middle (CM-stem), and middle-causative (MC-stem). Despite being not always present, the B-stem constitutes the base all other derivations operate on. Of course, these stems tend to lexicalise. So, it is sometimes opaque how different stems of the same verb belong semantically together. To explain the four valency changing stems beyond the B-stem, consider the figure below.

In this cross-classification, causative + causative is simply causative (the same concerning the mediopassive). The CM-stem (cf. *katena-* in the example) is very frequent in ṢUiṢuid but is also prone to a great deal of lexicalisation. In terms of hiatus avoidance, *ka-* becomes *k-* preceding vowels (e.g. *si-k-elpo* ‘I healed himself/herself’).

The derived valency changing stems for *tena* ‘to kill’

<i>tena</i> ‘to kill’	Causative	Mediopassive
Causative	<i>gu-tena-</i> ‘to commission contract killing’	<i>ka-tena-</i> ‘to get oneself killed, sacrifice oneself’
Mediopassive	<i>gu-ni-tena-</i> ‘to drive sb. to suicide’	<i>ni-tena-</i> ‘to get killed’

§2. The primary meaning of the **C-stem** is obviously ‘to make/let sb. do x’. Typical examples of causatives are *gulaxo-* ‘to kill’ (cf. *laxo-* ‘to die’), *gurumi-* ‘to show’ (cf. *rumi-* ‘to see’), *guḥaku-* ‘to ruin, devastate sb./sth.’ (cf. *ḥaku-* ‘to perish, decay’), *gulepo-* ‘to cure sb.’ (cf. *lepo-* ‘to be healthy, be doing well’), *guxeyu-* ‘to inform sb.’ (cf. *xeyu-* ‘to know’), or *gumaru-* ‘to make great, increase, enlarge, glorify sb./sth.’ (cf. *maru-* ‘to be big, be important’).

§3. Now we are looking at the **M-stem**. Middle semantics are quite complex. So, the reader is recommended to consult respective literature on that topic (such as some work by Artemis Alexiadou and Suzanne Kemmer). It often means a back reference to the subject similar to reflexivity. It can also mean that the event happens in the interest of the subject.

For representative instances of mediopassives, note the following forms: *niseña-* ‘to wash (oneself)’ (cf. *seña-* ‘to wash sb./sth.’), *nimixa-* ‘to ponder, speculate’ (cf. *mixa-* ‘to think’), or *niebu-* ‘to get free, get rid of sb./sth.; to become clear, comprehensible’ (cf. *ebu-* ‘to solve, decipher, untie, free sb./sth.’).

§4. With the causative stems in mind, consider some examples of the **CM-stem**. The respective meaning of a word in this stem is often predictable by turning the C-stem into the semantics of the mediopassive stem: *kalaxo-* ‘to kill oneself, commit suicide’, *karumi-* ‘to show oneself, appear’, *kaḥaku-* ‘to ruin oneself, perish (by own deeds, but accidentally)’, *kalepo-* ‘to cure oneself’, *kaxeyu-* ‘to inform oneself, get informed’, or *kamaru-* ‘to make oneself great, increase (intr.), grow, glorify oneself’.

§5. As opposed to the CM-stem, the **MC-stem** is slightly less frequent due to the fact that typically the verb root must be transitive. Here are some examples based on the verbs we have already seen: *guniseña-* ‘to make/let sb. wash (oneself)’, *gunimixa-* ‘to awake doubts in sb., make sb. doubt sth.’, *guniebu-* ‘to explain, make sb./sth. comprehensible’.

2.2.2 The aspectual stems

§1. The “aspectual stems” are diminutive, inchoative, and intensive. These stem modifications change the aktionart of the verb. They can freely combine with the valency changing stems and partly with each other, too. While the valency changing stems typically alter the argument frame of a verb (as the name says), the aspectual stems have an effect on the aktionsart. I won’t speak of *grammatical* aspect because of the derivational—i.e. lexical—character of these stems.

§2. The **inchoative stem**—also called **N-stem**—is primarily used for inherently durative, atelic verbs. Due to the inchoative/inceptive function, these verbs become punctual and telic. This stem signifies ongoing events but does not distinguish between slow and sudden events. Moreover, it can indicate a change of state (having mutative semantics). Two good examples are *demin-* ‘to become good, improve’ derived from *demi-* ‘to be good’ and *yuxom-* ‘to fall asleep’ which is derived from *yuxo-* ‘to sleep’. Here, the allomorphs of the N-stem become visible: The widest distribution has the suffix *-n*, but following back vowels, i.e. /u o/, it is *-m*. Thus, the name “N-stem” is not because of the *n*-suffix but should be understood as “Nasal stem”.

§3. The **reduplication stem (R-stem)** carries “intensive” semantics and is expressed by reduplication of the first stem syllable. Some examples with the meanings of the simple verb in brackets: *tetena-* ‘to massacre’ (‘to kill’), *lalaxo-* ‘to kick the bucket’ (‘to die’), *gualaxo-* ‘to murder’ (‘to kill, make sb. die’), *pepelu-* ‘to wait for a long time’ (‘to wait’), *iisa-* ‘to cut into pieces, carve’ (‘to cut’, pronounced as [ʔi:sa]), *vavañe-* ‘to drill, study intensively’ (‘to learn’), *kokolu-* ‘to be deep red’ (‘to be red’), *mumuña-* ‘to burn down (intr.)’ (‘to burn (intr.)’), *fufudu* ‘to toil, drudge’ (‘to work’), *luluke* ‘do/make repeatedly’, *duduhi-* ‘to defeat many’, *ruruvo-* ‘to sink’ (no B-stem), *dadalen-* ‘to become spring’ (‘to begin to blossom’), *nenexu-* ‘to conceive’ (‘to understand’), *xexeyu-* ‘to know much/many things’ (‘to know’), *gulelepo-* ‘to heal many (people)’, *ninixe-* ‘to get drunk’ (‘to drink (alcohol)’), *leleru-* ‘to run’ (‘to go’).

As we can see, the basic idea is that the event happens in an intensified way. This can be by stronger forces at hand but also as pluractional. In some cases, some verbs also get an iterative component.

§5. The **F-stem** is the **diminutive stem** being marked by the prefix *fi-*. The F-stem is insofar the most limited stem as it cannot be combined with the valency changing stems. To give a few examples: *finixe-* ‘to get half-drunk, squiffy’ (*nixe-* ‘to get drunk’), *fiɣudi-* ‘to whisper’ (*ɣudi-* ‘to talk, speak, say’), *fileru-* ‘to take a walk’ (*leru-* ‘to go, walk’), *fitena-* ‘to pretend killing’, *fizudo-* ‘to hop, leap’ (*zudo-* ‘to jump’).

In terms of semantics, the F-stem basically signifies that the event happens “just a little”. This often implies minimisation, hence, some cuteness of the event in the opinion of the speaker. In a couple of cases, it denotes the event takes place in a pseudo-manner, often to translate as ‘to pretend x-ing’.

2.3 Nominal Inflection

2.3.1 Nominal Number

§1. ΩUiΩuid nouns are inflected for number (singular vs. plural). The singular is unmarked, the plural is marked. There are three plural patterns: the lengthening plural (L-plural), the reduplicative plural (R-plural), and the plural marked by the suffix *-oo* (O-plural). The respective plural has to be learned though there are some broad regularities. It may be no coincidence that all plural forms share the property of having a stem-final heavy stressed syllable.

The L- and R-plural are the most frequent patterns, the O-plural is relatively rare but used for the majority of loan words. Below, some examples of the L-plural are listed. As one can see, words with /e/ as first vowel show some degree of free variance whereas those beginning in a consonant + /i/, /u/, or /o/ are more determined. Though there are nouns of the structure CaVC with L-plural, they are very rare. Nouns with only one vowel quality never follow this pattern.

Singular	Plural	IPA (plural)	Gloss
<i>waeb</i>	<i>waeeb</i>	wahe:b	‘letter, piece of writing’
<i>ail</i>	<i>aiil</i>	ʔahi:l	‘donkey’
<i>gaos</i>	<i>gaoos</i>	gaho:s	‘weight (measuremeant)’
<i>tauɟ</i>	<i>tauuɟ</i>	tahu:ɟ	‘finger’
<i>deal</i>	<i>deaal</i>	dejaal ~ dʔa:l	‘hole’
<i>peir</i>	<i>peiir</i>	peji:r ~ pʔi:r	‘fortress, castle’
<i>veoɣ</i>	<i>veooɣ</i>	vejo:ɣ ~ vʔo:ɣ	‘cucumber’
<i>neux</i>	<i>neuux</i>	neju:χ ~ nʔu:χ	‘eye’
<i>niav</i>	<i>niaav</i>	nʔa:v	‘mouth of a river, delta’
<i>sieb</i>	<i>sieeb</i>	sʔe:b	‘ear’
<i>siot</i>	<i>sioot</i>	sʔo:t	‘food, meal’
<i>hiup</i>	<i>hiuup</i>	hʔu:p	‘sapphire’
<i>toaħ</i>	<i>toaah</i>	tʔa:ħ	‘table, desk’
<i>goer</i>	<i>goer</i>	gʔe:r	‘issue, matter, thing’
<i>koik</i>	<i>koiik</i>	kʔi:k	‘blessing’

<i>roez</i>	<i>roeez</i>	r ^w e:z	‘palm’
<i>ñoud</i>	<i>ñouud</i>	ɲowu:d ~ ɲu:d	‘bill, invoice’
<i>uaf</i>	<i>uaaf</i>	wa:f	‘pine’
<i>sueh</i>	<i>sueeh</i>	s ^w e:h	‘wall’
<i>Ʊuid</i>	<i>Ʊuiid</i>	Ʊwi:d	‘language’
<i>zuod</i>	<i>zuood</i>	z ^w o:d	‘leap, jump’

§2. Nouns with only one vowel quality frequently show the R-plural, such as *book* vs. *bookook* ‘shackle(s)’ or *yas* ‘house’ vs. *yasaas* ‘houses’. As a rule of thumb, the last sequence of vowel + consonant is reduplicated. Consider the following examples:

Singular	Plural	Gloss
<i>rios</i>	<i>riosooos</i>	‘hand’
<i>houg</i>	<i>houguug</i>	‘lake’
<i>keis</i>	<i>keisiis</i>	‘dance’
<i>moev</i>	<i>moeveev</i>	‘bog, swamp’
<i>nuug</i>	<i>nuuguug</i>	‘god, goddess; star’
<i>paul</i>	<i>pauluul</i>	‘king, queen’
<i>raes</i>	<i>raesees</i>	‘lord, master’
<i>daug</i>	<i>dauguug</i>	‘building, house’

§3. The third type of nominal plural poses the O-plural, which is rather simple because just an *-oo* is suffixed to the stem. Examples are: *hiisoo* ‘questions’, *garaxoo* ‘horses’, *kuboo* ‘idiots’. The last two examples are loans.

2.3.2 Case Marking

§1. In its second developmental stage, ƱUiƱuid has four cases: nominative, genitive, accusative, and adverbial (oblique). This was largely expanded in the third conlanging stage since there are only very few natural languages with this number of cases. My original idea about these cases was the practical aspect. The nominative should be unmarked. The opposition to the accusative case should make the argument roles clear. A genitive proved to be highly useful in names whereby the adverbial case does everything else since context typically settles potential ambiguities; if one says “I met my sister at the market”, it is obvious that the word for ‘market’ has a locative function—not a causal, temporal, or concessive one.

Many prepositions require the adverbial case though some more recent ones are constructed with the genitive due to the grammaticalisation of former NP_{head} + NP_{dependent} constructions.

§2. The case system shall be illustrated by the noun *ʕuid* ‘language’. As is easily observable, the respective case ending does not change according to number. For the O-plural, the genitive is not *-ir* but just *-r*.

Case	Singular	Plural
Nom	<i>ʕuid</i>	<i>ʕuid</i>
Gen	<i>ʕuid-ir</i>	<i>ʕuid-r</i>
Acc.	<i>ʕuid-a</i>	<i>ʕuid-a</i>
Adv.	<i>ʕuid-e</i>	<i>ʕuid-e</i>

2.4 Verbal Inflection

ʕUʕuid exhibits two tenses which I call “present” and “past” tense even though these terms are slightly misleading because they are no absolute tenses but relative ones. The “present tense” does not necessarily imply that an event happens at the time of the utterance but signifies an event which takes place simultaneously in relation to the context. Consider the following utterance:

*Kom siotre pe Doume Yaokir. Nawa **siunka** donxota.*

‘Yesterday, I travelled to Doum Yaok. There, I **met** a priest.’

Though *siunka* is in the “present tense”, it does have the same meaning as in English but just continues the event of which the time is already given by *siotre* ‘I travelled’ in the “past tense”. Since *siotre* has no further context, it simply means the event lies in the past. If it were not *siunka* but *nukat* (in the “past tense”), the sentence would mean the meeting with the priest was before the journey to Doum Yaok. The ʕUʕuid tense system resembles in many ways that of Biblical Hebrew and Classical Arabic.

There are two number (singular and plural) and three persons whereby the first person plural distinguishes between inclusive and exclusive meaning.

2.4.1 The Present Tense

The so-called present tense combines the root in a CVCV-shape with suffixes as exponents for person. Number is expressed by lengthening of the last segment of the stem, leading to a stress shift.

In my first approaches to ʕUiʕuid morphology, all verbs were disyllabic. This is the predominant pattern in my second developmental stage. Note, however, the altered root structure in the third conceptual phase with many more CVC-roots. For those roots, lengthening in the plural works in a slightly different way. For *ʕek-* ‘to hit, strike’, the 3rd person pl. is *ʕekkar*, but for *tug-* ‘to pull’, it is *tuugar*, not **tuggar*. Lengthening depends on the kind of root-final consonant: In principle, the root-final consonant is lengthened except if it a voiced obstruent. In such cases, the root vowel is lengthened instead. Leaving Standard ʕUiʕuid, many dialects follow this pattern. But some do not exhibit compensatory lengthening and go without any plural marking. Other varieties just lengthen every root-consonant for CVC-roots no matter this consonant looks like.

The present tense

	Sg.	Pl.	
1	<i>dagu-at</i> [ˈda.ɡʷat]	excl.	<i>daguu-at</i> [da.ˈgu:.at]
		incl.	<i>daguu-al</i>
2	<i>dagu-am</i>		<i>daguu-am</i>
3	<i>dagu-ar</i>		<i>daguu-ar</i>

Dialectal divergence also plays a role in the pronunciation of final-*a* verbs, such as *tena-* ‘to kill’. In theory, the singular should be *tenaat*, *tenaam*, *tenaar* with stress on the first syllable and an unstressed second syllable. In fact, some speakers pronounce it exactly this way while others shorten these forms to *tenat*, *tenam*, *tenar*. The plural is always stressed on the long vowel (i.e. the final syllable in this example).

In the second conceptual phase, I only marginally thought about mood. I have not made a decision yet. But I am inclined to see the *a*-vowel in the present tense paradigm as marker of the indicative with an empty exponent for the subjunctive mood.

2.4.2 The Past Tense

§1. In the so-called past tense, person, and number are cumulatively expressed in a prefix which is attached to the root whose first two segments underwent metathesis (VCCV). In the standard variety, there is no number difference in the 3rd person. In some eastern dialects, people use to impose their own dialectal pattern also in the standard and lengthen the last vowel in the 3rd person plural in analogy to plural marking in the present tense and many nouns to make a difference between singular and plural, i.e. *dadguu* instead of standard *dadgu*. It does not surprise that some remote eastern dialects of a minority in a non-ᶒUiᶒuid speaking area generalised the lengthening plural over the whole plural paradigm. In consequence, the cumulative prefix exponent became obsolete and the prefixes of the singular were transferred to the plural + lengthened final vowel (e.g. *sadguu* instead of *ḥadgu* ‘you (pl.) built’).

The past tense in Standard ᶒUiᶒuid

	Sg.	Pl.	
1	<i>si-adgu</i> ['sʰad.gu]	excl.	<i>l-adgu</i>
		incl.	<i>j-adgu</i>
2	<i>s-adgu</i>		<i>ḥ-adgu</i>
3	<i>d-adgu</i>		<i>d-adgu(u)</i>

§2. A remark about the past tense. In my original proposal, there were distinct paradigms for the past tense of transitive and intransitive verbs. But since I have never been pleased with it, ᶒUiᶒuid still lacks the past tense paradigm for intransitive verbs. So one could argue there is only one paradigm for the past tense independently of valency.

§3. Now in my third developmental stage of ᶒUiᶒuid, I am still unsure about the status of metathesis. I have not fully opened my mind about that. For old *CVCə verbs such as *fam-* ‘to play (a game)’, I consider to establish the past tense bases *-af<a>m* and *-afm<a>* for different dialects. This loosely follows the observations of Broselow (1992) “Parametric Variation in Arabic Dialect Phonology” about CV- and VC-dialects. The epenthetic vowel in ᶒUiᶒuid shall be in total harmony with the stem vowel. Furthermore, I tend to make metathesis less primitive to ᶒUiᶒuid morphophonology but more epiphenomenal to create a heavy syllable. I recommend the reader the respective literature about metathesis in the

Malayo-Polynesian languages Rotuman and Amarasi though my main inspiration came from Saanich (a Salishan language).

§4. A further challenge for constructing ?Ui?uid will be the treatment of derived verbs. For instance, *gurumi-* ‘to show’ (C-stem of *rumi-* ‘to see’) should not be mapped on **sigurmi*, i.e. **/si+gu+urmi/*. The problem becomes even more salient for the rest of the prefixes. For the purely consonantal prefixes, such as *d-* in the 2nd person, the consonantal cluster in **dgurumi* would be ungrammatical because the phonotactic benefit between a consonantal prefix and the vowel-initial stem is lost. A solution could be an epenthetic or prosthetic vowel as in hypothetical *?digurumi* or *?idgurumi*.

There are two further problems: the phonological “purpose” of metathesis and locality. As mentioned above, creating heavy syllables and avoiding complex onsets are the possible goals from a functional point of view. Concerning locality, it is expected that the root firstly combines with a derivational head (such as causative *gu-*) and then the exponents of tense/agreement can be attached. Thus, it would be “unnatural” if we first build the past tense base *-urmi* from the root */rumi/* and then make it causative.

Assuming that only functionally adjacent elements can effect each other, we could establish an allomorphy rule. Let us consider metathesis as epiphenomenon, the exponent of tense would be a heavy syllable */H/*, which would effect the causative prefix */gu-/*. Possibly, *-ug-rumi* or *-guu-rumi* could be the outcome. While the former would solve the problem of the complex onset (*?dugrumi* ‘you (sg.) showed’), *?idguurumi* would still need a prosthetic vowel.

But there is another solution. We could establish a rule of allomorphy. In this account, the heavy syllable as exponent of tense depends on the syntactic node next to it. If the verb is not derived (assuming a vacuous Voice head), the Tense node is adjacent to the root:

$[\text{Tense H-} [\text{Voice } \emptyset\text{-} [\text{v} [\text{Root } \textit{rumi}]]]]$

But if a derivational affix such as *gu-* intervenes at the *v* node, the Tense node cannot be influenced by the root anymore but by *v*. In such cases, another allomorph than */H/* could appear. Let us say this alternative to */H/* is a vowel such as */e/*. In this case, the result would be the form *?degurumi* ‘you (sg.) showed’.

3. Syntax

Unfortunately, syntax remained the least developed part of ʕUiʕuid, standing in great contrast to my other conlang grammars for Horn and Tʷinneð Rēxa. Nonetheless, I may present here what I have created for ʕUiʕuid.

3.1 Syntactic Basics

The basic constituent order is VSO. Noun phrases can be “moved” in a topic position, making the impression of an SVO language. I have not made a decision about the position of adverbials. But I am inclined to place them at the beginning or end of a clause.

As the VSO order suggests, ʕUiʕuid is a left-headed language. Likewise, any kind of modifier follows its noun. ʕUiʕuid is devoid of postpositions featuring prepositions. There is no category for adjectives. Instead, nouns serve as modifiers. Thus, a ‘big city/town’ is *saik maurir*, lit. ‘a city/town of bigness’. For predication, no adjectives are needed since verbs do the same job: *maruar saik* ‘the/a city/town is white’. As one can see, ʕUiʕuid lacks definite and indefinite articles. Neither topic marking is present.

3.2 Personal Pronouns

ʕUiʕuid is a pro drop language, i.e. a pronominal subject is commonly omitted and only used for reinforcing the subject.

Personal Pronouns in the Nominative

	Singular	Plural	
1	<i>six</i>	excl.	<i>lire</i>
		incl.	<i>ali</i>
2	<i>sam</i>		<i>ħire</i>
3	<i>dio</i>		<i>dioor</i>

In the accusative case, the *-a* suffix simply attaches to the pronoun with some phonological interaction of the final vowel. For possession, the genitive with the *-(i)r* ending is used—along with a more progressive form as enclitic for the singular. The possessive pronouns in the plural did not lose their independence nor their phonological integrity.

Personal Pronouns in the Accusative

	Singular	Plural	
1	<i>sixa</i>	excl.	<i>lirya</i>
		incl.	<i>alya</i>
2	<i>sama</i>		<i>ħirya</i>
3	<i>diwa</i>		<i>dioora</i>

Possessive Pronouns

	Singular	Plural	
1	<i>sixir ~ sir</i>	excl.	<i>lirer</i>
		incl.	<i>alir</i>
2	<i>samir ~ sar</i>		<i>ħirer</i>
3	<i>diwir ~ dir</i>		<i>dioorir</i>